

Teacher Recruitment and Selection Process: A Case of Selected International Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia

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Abstract:

Overview: This study was designed to investigate teacher recruitment and selection process in selected international secondary schools in Lusaka, Zambia with specific reference to its impact.

Body of Knowledge: The study delves into the methodologies and practices adopted to attract, evaluate, and hire educators. It explores the criteria used to assess candidates' qualifications, competencies, and suitability for the roles within these institutions. The study investigated the balance between academic credentials, teaching experience, and personal attributes in the selection process.

Methods: The study employed a descriptive survey research design. The approach was mainly through qualitative methods of data collection and analysis, using themes and sub-themes drawn from in-depth personal interviews. The qualitative approach was however supplemented with quantitative material obtained using self-administered semi-structured questionnaires. The study sample consisted 100 respondents; 4 current and 4 former vice principals of secondary sections, including 46 serving and 46 former secondary schools teachers in four international secondary schools in Lusaka. The qualitative data was analyzed thematically whereas the quantitative data was analyzed using Microsoft word and SPSS to come up with graphs, charts and tables.

Results: The study established that the highest percentage of teachers teaching in the international schools were recruited on referral basis, indicating a closed system of recruitment in which teachers with previous experiences in similar schools stood better chances of being recruited. Findings further showed that academic credentials were a key determinant to recruitment. Additionally, the study found that while most foreign teachers were recruited with a minimum of two years teaching experience, findings indicated that Zambian teachers had to have longer teaching experiences of about 5 to 10 years.

Recommendation: Government should implement standardized criteria for evaluating candidates that align with the school's values, educational philosophy, and specific needs. This could include academic qualifications, teaching experience, pedagogical skills, and alignment with the school's mission.

Keywords: Credentials Verification, Education Policy, International Schools, Selection Process, and Teacher Recruitment.

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Teacher recruitment is the process of attracting, identifying, and selecting individuals to fill teaching positions within educational institutions. It involves a series of steps, including advertising vacancies, screening applications, conducting interviews, and evaluating candidates' qualifications and fit for the role (Wamalwa & Burns, 2018). Effective teacher recruitment aims to ensure that schools and educational systems have access to highly qualified, skilled, and motivated teachers who can meet the diverse needs of students and contribute to the overall quality of education. This process often involves collaboration between school administrators, human resource departments, and sometimes external recruitment agencies, to ensure a thorough and efficient selection of the best candidates.

The selection process in teacher recruitment refers to the systematic procedure used by educational institutions to evaluate and choose the most suitable candidates for teaching positions (Walsh, 2019). This process typically involves several stages, including the initial screening of applications to shortlist candidates who meet the minimum qualifications, conducting interviews to assess their skills, knowledge, and fit with the school's culture, and often, practical teaching demonstrations to evaluate their instructional abilities in a classroom setting. Additional steps may include reference checks and background verifications to ensure the credibility and reliability of the candidates (Tamir, 2021). The aim of the selection process is to identify and hire teachers who are not only qualified but also align with the institution's educational philosophy and goals, thereby contributing positively to the learning environment and overall educational outcomes.

Education policy in teacher recruitment refers to the principles and guidelines set by educational authorities and institutions to govern the hiring process of educators. These policies aim to ensure that schools attract, select, and retain qualified and competent teachers who can effectively contribute to student learning and school improvement (Sylvester, 2014). Such policies often include criteria for teacher qualifications, procedures for application and selection, standards for professional conduct, and strategies for professional development. The goal is to create a fair, transparent, and efficient recruitment process that aligns with the broader educational objectives and standards, ultimately enhancing the quality of education provided to students. Effective education policies in teacher recruitment are essential for addressing teacher shortages, promoting diversity in the teaching workforce, and ensuring that all students have access to high-quality education.

Despite a growing body of work on teacher recruitment and selection worldwide, there is little significant research available concentrating on teacher recruitment and selection in international school settings (MoE, 2014). This is quite surprising given that international schools have been characterized as experiencing a relatively high staff turnover (Hanushek, 2016). A synopsis of the studies reviewed in general on teacher recruitment and selection focused on recruitment models, teacher quality and effectiveness as the basis for recruitment, appointment based on teacher categories, teacher supply and demand, teacher turnover, recruitment and selection based

on market segmentation and the use of specialized recruiters to recruit teachers. However, there appears to be very little research providing operational guidance on the process of employee recruitment in terms of policy and practice. While much is written about the process of employee selection in other occupations, there has been little discussion on the process and tools of teacher selection and why it occurs the way it does (Han, 2018). In the case of international schools, this scenario is dire given their dispersed locations and diverse circumstances. In the absence of documented research, the recruitment and selection process of international school teachers will continue to be construed as ‘unusual, if not bizarre’.

From the Zambian perspective, it equally appears that there are currently no studies done on teacher selection and recruitment in international schools, although a study was conducted on the development and role of multi-racial private schools in Zambia (Chilufya 2016). A knowledge gap therefore does exist from an international and local perspective that needs to be filled especially when one considers the fact that private multi-cultural international schools have been in existence globally since the 1860s (Sylvester, 2014) and in Zambia since 1962 (Sikwibele, 2016). This topic is an area of concern because if the study is not undertaken, the recruitment and selection of teachers in international schools will continue to remain ‘a well-kept secret’, consequently precluding the participation of Zambian teachers intending to teach in these schools. The myth that Zambian teachers lack the requisite qualifications and experience to teach in international schools will also continue to be perpetuated. In order for Zambia to attain its national goal of equity and equality in education as declared in its policy documents (Educating Our Future 1996, and Zambia Vision 2030, and Chanda & Madoda, 2024) it was critically important that the study was undertaken to curtail any form of unequitable and discriminatory teacher recruitment and selection policies and practices that might exist in international schools.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The study examined teacher recruitment and selection in selected international secondary schools in Lusaka, Zambia with specific reference to policy and practice. Studies conducted internationally show that although there is a substantial body of work on teacher recruitment and selection in general, very little research has been done in the area of teacher recruitment and selection in international schools. Research further shows that there is no established operational guidance on how the process of teacher recruitment in international schools is conducted (Republic of Zambia, 2012). If this study on teacher recruitment and selection in selected international secondary schools in Lusaka was not undertaken, probably teacher selection and recruitment policies and practices in international schools would continue to remain unknown, consequently precluding the participation of Zambian teachers intending to teach in these elitist schools. The myth that Zambian teachers lack the requisite qualifications and experience to teach in international schools would also continue to exist in certain sections of Zambian society (Mutungwa, 2011). Furthermore, if teacher recruitment and selection processes are not examined in these schools, the national goal of attaining equity and equality

of education through teacher participation in education will continue to be elusive for the nation to attain (MoE, 1996). It is critically important that the study is undertaken to curtail any form of unequitable and discriminatory teacher recruitment and selection policies and practices that might exist in international schools.

1.3. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Establish the preferred teacher academic credentials in order to have qualified teachers in the selected international secondary schools in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Determine the nature of supply and demand of teachers in reference to teacher recruitment policies and practices in the schools in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Assess the extent to which teacher recruitment is affected by a teacher's cultural orientation in Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.4. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine teacher recruitment and selection process in selected multicultural international secondary schools in Lusaka, Zambia with a view of establishing the prevailing policies and practices on teacher recruitment and selection in these schools.

1.5. Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the Social Exchange Theory which supposes that motivational tasks performed between the workers and the organization give rise to organizational commitment of the workers. Based on this theory, workers join an organization while expecting that the organization would provide a good working environment as well as a good culture (Muleya et al, 2024). The workers therefore try the best means and methods of using their knowledge and skills to achieve organizational objectives. In effect, the positive relationship between the organization and its workers give rise to improved worker commitment to the organization. The social exchange theory postulates that a causal relationship is formed between the worker and the organization, which ensures an exchange between organizational culture and organizational commitment that positively affects organizational performance. Social exchange theory is based on three philosophies, namely reciprocity, rationality and specificity to expound the correlation between the workers and their employer (Foster & Schwartz, 2019). The reciprocity principle assumes that the social interaction between the workers and the organization is usually reciprocal in nature such that the worker gains from the organization's positive outlook while the organization gains from the employees' satisfaction. The rationality principle assumes that the workers usually exhibit a positive relationship with an organization that provides positive returns that can satisfy the wants and needs of the workers. Specificity principle, on the other hand, mutual benefit type of relationship can endure a kind of switch over rapport between the workers and the company.

1.6. Significance of the Study

The study holds significant importance for several reasons. Firstly, it aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current practices and criteria used in hiring educators, which is crucial for ensuring high-quality education. By examining these processes, the study can identify best practices and potential areas for improvement, thereby contributing to the enhancement of

educational standards. Additionally, the findings can offer insights into how international schools attract and retain skilled teachers, which is vital for maintaining a competitive edge in the global education market. Furthermore, this research has the potential to influence policy-making and administrative decisions, ultimately leading to more effective recruitment strategies that align with the schools' educational goals and the diverse needs of students. Lastly, the study can serve as a valuable resource for other educational institutions in Zambia and beyond, providing a model for effective teacher recruitment and selection processes that can be adapted to different contexts.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Global Trends in Teacher Recruitment in International Schools

Studies conducted internationally show that although there is a substantial body of work on teacher recruitment and selection in general, very little research has been done in the area of teacher recruitment and selection in international schools (Chudgar et al, 2014). This is quite surprising especially given that international schools have been characterized as experiencing a relatively high staff turn-over. From a global perspective, different researchers have focused on different aspects of the teacher recruitment and selection process. The themes identified in the literature reviewed on the topic are arguments to recruit international teachers based on the quality of teachers, appointment criteria, modes of searching for recruits, the recruitment and selection process, and factors influencing teacher supply and demand. The Commonwealth Secretariat (2003) affirms this position by categorically stating that 'quality and effectiveness in education can be measured by the pivotal role played by teachers.' Based on this premise some practitioners in recruitment and selection of teachers emphasize that the choice of teachers be based on teacher quality and effectiveness (Garton, 2021 and OECD, 2019). Attention has turned from concern over having a sufficient number of teachers to a concern about having a sufficient number of quality teachers.' The recruitment and selection of teachers therefore becomes a critical responsibility of educational leaders who must face up to the challenge of ensuring that their schools promote student achievement and quality education. The process of recruiting the best teachers however is a difficult task in itself as it is beset with challenges ranging from teacher turnover to problems associated with the difficulty of measuring teacher quality (Ivancevich, 2010).

2.2 Teacher Recruitment and Selection in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA)

Education International (2007) notes that there is an apparent insufficient recruitment of qualified teachers and the prevalent employment of unqualified, volunteer, contract or para teachers in Sub-Saharan Africa. This scenario is further amplified by the World Bank (2015) report which states that most SSA countries have a shortage of qualified mathematics and science teachers. With expansion, the report notes that primary teachers are teaching at secondary levels. In Eritrea for example the report indicates that most middle school teachers in government schools, 66% are only qualified at the elementary level and in Malawi 61.5% of secondary teachers are actually

primary teachers who have transferred to secondary schools. Chanda & Mwila (2023)' study further observed that attrition of mathematics and science teachers is higher compared to other subjects and the greatest cause being resignation and mostly among secondary rather than primary teachers. Other studies also associate the high attrition of teachers to the high HIV prevalence rate in some of the countries (Kelly, 2015). Ibid (2007) in its survey of Anglophone African countries which included the Gambia, Kenya, Lesotho, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia on recruitment, supply and retention of teachers brings to light another worrying dimension to the scenario which is government failure to recruit qualified teachers in SSA. The survey noted that: 'there was an apparent inability of governments to recruit adequate numbers of qualified teachers in most of the participating countries and others that either the country does not have enough qualified teachers, or it has failed to recruit them.'

Teacher recruitment and selection processes in Africa can vary significantly depending on the country. In some regions, there is a focus on academic qualifications, while in others, practical teaching skills and experience are prioritized. Cultural sensitivity and the ability to work in diverse and challenging environments may also be considered during the selection process (Chanda, 2024). In North America, teacher recruitment often involves advertising open positions through job boards, school district websites, and educational organizations. Candidates are typically required to submit their resumes, cover letters, and relevant documents, such as transcripts and certifications. The selection process may include multiple rounds of interviews, including panel interviews with administrators and teachers. Background checks and reference checks are commonly conducted to ensure the suitability of candidates (Jabbar, 2018). In European countries like Finland and Sweden, teacher recruitment processes are highly competitive. These countries prioritize candidates with strong academic backgrounds, often requiring a master's degree in education or a specific subject area. The selection process may include written exams, interviews, and teaching demonstrations. In some regions, teacher candidates are also assessed on their understanding of educational theory and pedagogy (Kingdon, 2020).

The review of literature presented above revealed that the tragedy of the Zambian education system in the public sector is so many schools without qualified teachers, yet there are so many qualified teachers without schools. According to the MoE (2004) there were 8,143 teachers in Zambian high schools in 2004. Thirty of these were untrained, 29 were holders of a preschool certificate, while 794 were holders of a primary teachers' certificate. According to the same ministerial bulletin, the minimum qualification for a high school teacher in Zambia was a bachelor's degree, yet only 12% of the teachers were holders of a bachelor's degree or higher qualification. This means that 88% of teachers teaching in Zambian high schools at the time were under qualified. This scenario had not changed much by 2014 as can be seen from the Educational Statistical Bulletin of that year. According to Ibid (2014) there were 2,465 teachers with a primary teacher's certificate and 13,300 teachers with a basic/secondary diploma teaching in secondary schools. There were only 4,945 degree holders representing 24% of teachers with a supposedly minimum qualification to teach in

most subjects. Although there was an increase of 8.2% in the number of teachers recruited from 2013 to 2014 due to the government policy to employ more teachers to improve access to education in the country, teacher attrition has continued to increase - teacher attrition in 2014 was 9,686 in contrast to 8,893 in 2013. Teacher recruitment in Zambian international schools can therefore be described as many schools with under qualified teachers, yet there are many qualified teachers unemployed. The teacher statistics discussed above denote also a situation in the public school system in Zambia.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

The method of recruitment entails sourcing, advertising, interviewing, and selecting future workers in an organization. According to Akiba et al (2017), the recruitment process involves conscription and training of new workers in their roles in the new work. Staff recruitment and selection lie at the center of human resources management's perception of sustaining competitive advantage over business rivals. The method of recruitment entails sourcing, advertising, interviewing, and selecting future workers in an organization. According to Mataka et al (2024), for a business entity to attain and maintain a competitive advantage over its rivals, it should treat each step in the recruitment and selection very carefully. The effect of decisions made during these processes will have long-term effects on the organization, with high economic effects, especially if the process has some pitfalls (Hanushek et al, 2014). Hardman (2019) indicates that organizations should adopt universal HR management which is tailored to provide the basis of achieving better results from the organizational workers. Some of the steps required in planning for recruitment include analysis of recruitment strengths, weaknesses, candidate requirements, and identification of candidates' sources. Beyani (2019) explains that an active recruitment program appeals to many potential applicants. When the number of applicants is large, the employing organization has an enormous pool of potential employees from which to pick the best among them.

2.4 Resource-Based View

The RBV (Resource-Based View) is a management structure applied to establish the strategic assets and funds that an organization can use to attain a continuous competitive edge (Barney, 1991). The emergence of this theory is closely associated with a 1991 article by Barney, titled "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage". The theory suggests that organizations are diverse as they have various resources, implying that they can have different strategies due to the unusual mix of resources. The approach concentrates on the organizational managers' attention to the organization's internal resources to discover the resources, capacities, and proficiency with the probability of attaining a higher sustainable advantage. A resource-based view refers to a multidiscipline method that symbolizes a considerable change in the line of thinking (Boyd, 2015). It is interdisciplinary because its development involves the subjects of economics, management, ethics, general business, law, and supply chain management. The resource-based view theory emphasizes the resources of an enterprise as necessary for organizing procedures and attaining a competitive advantage. In effect, Ibid (2019) asserted that for assets to possess capacity as a means

of competitive edge, the support needs to be imperfectly imitable, rare, valuable, and not replaceable. Thus, organizations need to develop exclusive competencies that enhance their better performance than opponents by carrying out their processes in different ways from their competitors.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Banda et al (2017) asserts that research designs and methods of social research are closely linked to different visions of how social reality should be examined. For the purpose of this study, descriptive research was therefore used to gain an insight into the school administrators' and the teachers' opinions regarding the prevailing teacher recruitment and selection policies in international schools. This approach enabled the study to capture a broad spectrum of data, encompassing numerical information through surveys and deeper, contextual insights via interviews. The study was conducted in 4 international secondary schools within Lusaka district. The target population for the study was 1000, with a sample size of 100 respondents which was 10% of the target population. The sample comprised of 4 former heads of secondary, 4 current heads of secondary at the time of the study, and 92 former and serving teachers comprising both Zambians and non-Zambians drawn from four international schools in Lusaka. Separate semi-structured questionnaires were given to heads of secondary and teachers. In order to triangulate the data from questionnaires, oral interviews were also held with former and current heads of secondary (vice principals). The qualitative data from interviews was analyzed based on themes and sub-themes that emerged through thematic analysis and presented in narrative and direct quotes as suggested by Oswala (2020). The data from the interviews, questionnaires and documents was analyzed to determine emerging themes related to the research questions. The quantitative data from questionnaires was first edited, coded before analyzing it using SPSS to come up with graphs, charts and tables. With regards to ethical consideration, participants were treated with respect and dignity and were accorded the right to privacy by concealing their identities in the study. The study also ensured that consent was obtained from participants before their participation in the study.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

4.1.1. The Preferred Teacher Academic Credentials

Data collected from the study revealed that there is a disparity between what is stated in the Zambian Qualifications Authority and what is actually found in the process of selecting which teacher does teach in the selected private secondary schools in the district of Lusaka. Most Zambian teachers have proven that they have the necessary papers that can make them reach out to public schools both local and international. This is as deduced from the sector of publication as

deduced from the section of the people that were talked to. Such as comments as; the Zambian syllabus suits Zambian only, echoes in the researcher that international schools' syllabi could be showing a different set of needs as compared to the Zambian set up (Moonga, 2015). Looking at the nature of the answers coming from the respondents from the selected schools, there is a clear assertion that much of what students are taught from the colleges and the existing universities is anchored on the prevailing Zambian curriculum. There has been a lot of talk on the manner of screening potential teachers from the inception of the Grade twelve certificates. However, the majority of the respondents did allude to the fact that there is still room for manipulation on the part of the operators. Having received such an allegation from some respondents, Zohaib et al (2024)' study pointed out that this finding leaves room of doubt in the kind of teachers that are admitted in the existing colleges and universities in line with those doing teaching training.

So then, the above assertion is aligned to the idea that the challenge of having to admit the teachers in the identified private international secondary schools starts from teacher training. At one of the sampled school, all the teachers who answered the administered questionnaires did state that there is a little disparity in the way the international schools embrace the Zambian curriculum and their expectation. Much of this speculation comes in as a result of the focus group discussions held in all the four sampled schools. Having sort for information on the right qualification from three different District Educational Board Secretaries; it is clear that there is defence shown in terms of the diploma and degree holders to be qualifying to teach in all these schools that are in existence. This notion of who qualifies to teach in all the international schools was received with reservations as all the people who answered that question to do with qualifications were inclined to believe that Zambian teachers are indeed equal to the task of teaching just as any other expatriate teacher (Mboozu et al, 2024). In explaining their decision making around teacher recruitment and selection, Zambian teachers in particular – all interviewees acknowledged that teacher recruitment and selection was either already challenging, or was likely to become more difficult. This was true of schools that were sampled across a wide range of circumstances, and was the context within which they framed their responses and decisions around teacher recruitment. Most school administrators who had recruited Zambian teachers in the last three years described doing so as a necessary 'last resort' or an additional strategy for overcoming the local shortage of teachers, as opposed to being a desirable option. The majority of schools that had not recruited Zambian teachers in the last three years reported not doing so because they currently did not need to, or because of negative experiences with Zambian teacher recruitment in the past. Below is a diagrammatical explanation of the preferred qualifications for teachers to be considered in the selected schools under study. Many who were recruited in the past three years are master's degree holder. However, the extreme recruits are certificate holder most the auxiliary staff.

Figure 1: Recruitment and Selection Terms of Qualifications in the Past Three Years

Figure 1 above presented concerns which were raised around the perceived effectiveness of Zambian teacher recruits and their ability to adapt quickly to the demands of the selected international secondary schools. There was little mention of any credentials being inadequate or adequate. Other barriers to international recruitment included practicalities such as understanding qualification equivalences and financial constraints notably. Most school Administrators felt strongly that they should not need to recruit locally trained Zambian teachers and that more should be done to ensure a sufficient supply of internationally trained or oriented teachers, including taking steps to improve the retention of existing teachers. Some school head teachers cited a need for additional information, support and guidance in order to make a more fully informed decision about whether to appoint Zambian locally trained teachers. This had a strong bearing on the allegation that, locally earned credentials were of low value compared to those that got their training abroad (Chanda, 2024). As a matter of getting the preferred credentials, schools often relied on Skype or telephone interviews and references to assess the suitability of candidates. This was done in this way because a lot of the mentors of the selected Secondary schools were based abroad but would be the ones to get to know which sort of credentials would be suitable for one to teach at such a school. Being unable to observe their classroom practice was seen as a major drawback, leading to variability in the quality of appointments. Candidates coming from countries where administrators had origins were more likely to attend interviews in person. In this way, Zambian credentials seemed less recognized.

4.1.2. Levels of Experienced Zambian Teachers in Comparison with Non-Zambian Teachers in the Past Four Years

This study further extended to investigate into the work experience needed by both a local and expatriate teacher. This is so because most of the times work experience becomes one of the qualifications for one to get a job not only in the teaching fraternity but as well as in other sector of life. Much information gathered shows an imbalance of what is expected between the two kinds of teacher’s origins mentioned.

Figure 2: Levels of Experienced Zambian Teachers in Comparison with Non-Zambian Teachers in the Past Four Years

According to figure 2 above, the levels of work experience from 2021 to 2022 shows a big gap. However, with the incentives being brought forth to this cause, the gap keeps narrowing as we get to 2024. In an in-depth interview and focus group discussions were held for the teachers and some administrators, most of them mentioned that there is no big gap in terms of work experience expected for international schools as compared to the locally established ones. There was a sure admission that private international school standards expected the people who would love to work in such got no only experience in international schools but good experience. Many teachers echoed the fact that a big challenge exists in the sense that one almost all international schools would ask for work experience when no institution is ready to give a chance for one to have such or that very experience they wish to see. The teachers in the selected secondary school generally have

experience of employment. In response to the question of whether they have ever held a job 83% say that they have while only 17% have never held a job. There was no significant difference between males and females in regard to having held a job. As one might expect from the differences among teachers in terms of which college or university one had been trained, teachers who had an experience break between school and college significantly favored work experience compared to teachers who came through direct study interestingly, the relationship between year of enrolment and the desirability of work experience was not significant. By and larger the overwhelming responses from the respondents was that those teachers with work experience stood a better chance of recruitment compared to those without work experience.

Alluding to the demand for work experience for a teacher to qualify to teach in international secondary school; all the teacher respondents strongly based their idea that as one is being trained to be a teacher, there is always a break for one to go on teaching practice. Darling-Hammond (2020) noted that as such that time out of collage is work experience for one to get a job at an international secondary school. However, there could be variations in individual teachers, but what is common us that they go to practice at actual school which are potential institutions for their future employment. As one courageous teacher stated:

“Practice teaching is an important component towards becoming a teacher. It provides experiences to student teachers in the actual teaching and learning environment”.

During teaching practice, a student-teacher is given the opportunity to try the art of teaching before actually getting into the real world of the teaching profession. Student teachers also know the value of teaching practice and they perceive it as the important aspect of their preparation for the teaching profession since it provides for the real interface between student hood and membership of the profession (Mpolomoka, et al, 2017). It is argued that a teacher cannot address the knowledge of subject matter to the students unless an appropriate teaching method is used. Also having more knowledge of the subject matter is thought to be the base to produce competent technologist. About 90% of the respondents saw that the curriculum content emphasizes more on the teaching skills and experience since it is what is needed during their education training program while 10% noted to emphasize less on the knowledge of the subject matter than practical skills. In as much as the majority of respondents claimed that teaching practice for student teachers renders enough capability for teacher recruitment and selection in international, there is also the other side of the coin. Majority of school administrator said that; student’s teachers are relatively less interested to learn more than passing examinations, instructors over load the learners at the end of the semester, cover one chapter in a single period and others fail to cover relevant chapters of the course. Most examinations are always prepared in a way that encourages the student teacher to write memorized lecture notes and handouts than critical thinking on the concept.

Instructors are overloaded and some of them are forced to handle courses in which they are not specialized. There are a large number of student teachers with a shortage of relevant reference materials. The study indicated that there is a problem of late beginning of teaching practice and

TP supervisors are unable to manage the large number of student teachers due to lack of coordination and follow up of problems. Peterson & Tracy (2019) noted that teaching practice program gives no attention to satisfy the needs and interest of the student teachers and supervisors. Henceforth the claim that teaching practice is enough work experience for teacher selection and recruitment is rendered devoid of the cause. As a matter of extending the investigation, respondents were further given room to determine the demand and supply of teachers in the selected international secondary schools. This was in view of establishing how this does affect teacher recruitment and supply. It is obvious that when there is low demand of teacher it follows that there would be less recruitment and selection. Likewise, when there is high demand, then the selection and recruitment of teachers gets high. However, findings to this regard varied from one school to the other. Almost all respondents aligned their feedback to the fact that the number of teachers selected and recruited in the sampled secondary school did not match the demands in all schools. It was noted by many that responded to questionnaires that there exists a disparity. While teacher preparation programs are producing enough teachers to meet the overall demand for teachers in these international secondary schools, there exists a discrepancy between the number of teachers needed in specific grade levels, subject areas, and regions, and the number produced in Zambian institutions of higher education (Chanda, 2023). In comparison, the vacancy rate for special education teachers was deemed to be a great compromise. The figure simply illustrates that the finding is that there is high demand of teachers especially in special education. Demand and supply of teachers is a concept of binary opposition as shown in the results. Demand of teachers is high and this entails that there is low supply especially in special education (Pergamon Millican, 2019).

4.2. The Nature of Supply and Demand of Teachers in Reference to Teacher Recruitment Policies and Practices in the Schools in Lusaka District

The study results showed that the one-to-one interaction with teaching personnel, it has been realized that there a cry of teachers in some specific areas of concern. Zambian teacher preparation institutions prepare more teachers than needed in the areas of early childhood education, social studies and physical education (Chanda & Siyunda, 2023). Previous years' studies identified middle school education as shortage areas. At the same time, preparation institutions continue to under-produce teachers in special education, mathematics and foreign language, among other specializations. Hence the demand-supply ratio is never at equilibrium. Based on the inquiry made from the incumbent teachers and managers in the selected multicultural international secondary schools, there is not visible or direct connection between a teacher's cultural orientation and recruitment. However, some respondents gave convincing reasons of that very connection in the manner stated below. Many respondents mentioned that a teacher's cultural orientation ought to find room in the existing organizational or school cultural establishment. In as much as the individual teacher could have a bias in the manner they carry themselves, there should not be any form conflict with that culture brought forth by the organization or institution in any way (Abdou, 2019). They believe that; culture of adaptability facilitates the transition of external demands and

teacher expectations into internal changes of a school. Furthermore, this trait is considered to be a defensive capacity for responding to unexpected environmental threats (Breugh & Starke, 2017). Moreover, those employees (teachers in this case) who espouse the trait of adaptability can express themselves in wide-ranging behaviours.

Figure 3: Demand of Teachers and Supply of Teachers

Figure 4: Nature of Supply and Demand of Teachers

4.3. The Extent to Which Teacher Recruitment Is Affected by A Teacher's Cultural Orientation in Lusaka District

According to study results, the extent to which teacher recruitment is affected by a teacher's cultural orientation in Lusaka District can be understood by examining various factors and their impacts on the recruitment process. The study found Cultural Background and Diversity at 25%, Language Proficiency at 25%, Adaptability and Flexibility at 34%, Training and Professional Development at 8%, and Policy and Regulations at 8%. Table 1 below summarized these findings.

Table 1: The Extent to Which Teacher Recruitment Is Affected by A Teacher's Cultural Orientation

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Cultural Background and Diversity	15	25%
Language Proficiency	15	25%
Adaptability and Flexibility	50	34%
Training and Professional Development	10	8%
Policy and Regulations	10	8%
Total	100	100%

In Lusaka District, the cultural background and diversity of teachers play a significant role in the recruitment and selection processes of international secondary schools. The multicultural environment of these institutions necessitates a diverse teaching staff capable of connecting with students from various cultural backgrounds. Chitondo & Chanda (2023) says that diversity is about what makes each of us unique and includes our backgrounds, personality, life experiences and beliefs, all of the things that make us who we are. This diversity is not only beneficial but often essential in fostering an inclusive and effective educational setting. Schools are increasingly aware that teachers who possess a deep understanding and appreciation of different cultures can contribute to a more dynamic and engaging learning experience. Therefore, cultural orientation can significantly influence recruitment decisions, with schools seeking candidates who demonstrate cultural competence and sensitivity. The impact of a teacher's cultural orientation on their recruitment is multifaceted. Firstly, teachers who are culturally aware and adaptable are often better equipped to address the diverse needs of students, creating an inclusive classroom environment. This capability is particularly crucial in international schools where students come from various cultural and linguistic backgrounds (Boyd et al, 2016). Recruiters prioritize

Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 16 July 2024

Accepted: 20 July 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12786611>

candidates who exhibit these qualities, recognizing their potential to enhance student engagement and academic performance. Moreover, culturally oriented teachers can act as cultural brokers, helping to bridge cultural gaps between the school and the broader community, which can foster stronger relationships and a more cohesive school culture.

Additionally, the recruitment process in Lusaka's international secondary schools often includes assessments of a candidate's cultural competency. This may involve evaluating their previous experience in multicultural settings, their ability to incorporate diverse perspectives into their teaching practices, and their commitment to promoting cultural understanding among students. Chanda (2024) supported this finding by adding that cultural factors encompass a broad spectrum of elements that shape societies, communities, and individuals. These factors include traditions, customs, beliefs, values, languages, norms, rituals, arts, and social institutions that are shared by a particular group of people. They play a pivotal role in shaping identities, behaviors, and interactions among individuals within a society. Schools might also consider the cultural alignment between potential teachers and the school's values and mission. Candidates who align well with these aspects are viewed as assets who can uphold and enhance the school's cultural diversity and inclusivity goals (Ola, 2014). However, the emphasis on cultural background and diversity in teacher recruitment can also present challenges (Engel, 2013) For instance, it might limit the pool of applicants if the criteria are too stringent or specific, potentially overlooking qualified candidates who might lack extensive multicultural experience but possess other valuable skills. Additionally, there can be tensions between striving for cultural diversity and ensuring that all candidates are evaluated fairly and without bias. Schools must navigate these challenges carefully to maintain a balanced and equitable recruitment process.

Furthermore, the findings indicated that language proficiency plays a crucial role in teacher recruitment, often influencing the extent to which a teacher's cultural orientation impacts their eligibility for positions within educational institutions. Language proficiency is not merely about the ability to communicate effectively but also encompasses the teacher's understanding and fluency in languages used for instruction, such as English (Chitondo et al, 2024). Teachers with a high level of proficiency in English are typically preferred due to its status as the primary language of instruction in Zambian schools, including those in Lusaka District. This proficiency is essential for effectively conveying subject matter and interacting with students, parents, and fellow educators (Kalasa et al, 2023). Cultural orientation also factors into teacher recruitment, reflecting how well a teacher's background aligns with the cultural context of the school and community. While cultural diversity can enrich educational environments, particularly in promoting inclusivity and understanding, institutions often prioritize candidates whose cultural orientation complements local norms and values. Peter (2012) alluded that this alignment is perceived to contribute positively to classroom dynamics, student engagement, and overall school cohesion.

The respondents alluded that in teacher recruitment processes are influenced by the adaptability and flexibility of candidates, particularly in relation to their cultural orientation. Adaptability refers to the ability of teachers to adjust to new environments, educational systems, and student demographics (Kampala, 2015). Schools often prioritize candidates who demonstrate a willingness and capability to integrate into diverse cultural settings within Zambia's educational landscape. One of the school principals expressed that:

“Teachers who are adaptable and willing to integrate into the local community may be seen as more favorable candidates. This includes being open to learning and respecting local traditions and norms”.

Flexibility, on the other hand, pertains to teachers' capacity to adapt their teaching methods, communication styles, and instructional strategies to meet the needs of diverse student populations. In Lusaka District, where cultural diversity is significant, schools seek teachers who can navigate and respect various cultural norms, languages, and learning traditions prevalent among students (Chanda, 2024). The extent to which a teacher's cultural orientation affects recruitment lies in their ability to demonstrate awareness and appreciation of local customs, values, and educational expectations. Teachers who exhibit cultural competence, sensitivity, and a proactive approach in incorporating local context into their teaching practice are often preferred during the recruitment process (Pelekamoyo, 2017).

The study results also noted that the recruitment of teachers is significantly influenced by their cultural orientation, which impacts training and professional development practices. Cultural orientation plays a pivotal role in shaping teachers' pedagogical approaches, classroom management styles, and overall integration into the educational system (Ellis et al, 2017). Training programs often emphasize cultural sensitivity and awareness, aiming to equip teachers with the skills to navigate diverse classroom environments effectively. Professional development initiatives focus on enhancing cultural competency, promoting inclusive teaching practices, and fostering respect for local traditions and values. These efforts are crucial in ensuring that teachers can effectively engage with students from various cultural backgrounds, thereby improving educational outcomes and fostering a more inclusive learning environment (Chanda, 2024). However, challenges may arise when cultural orientations diverge significantly from institutional norms or when there is a lack of alignment between teachers' cultural backgrounds and the educational context in which they operate. This mismatch can impact teacher retention rates and overall job satisfaction, highlighting the importance of culturally responsive recruitment strategies that consider both qualifications and cultural fit (Kipsoi & Antony, 2018).

Teachers explained that teacher recruitment policies and regulations play a critical role in shaping the extent to which a teacher's cultural orientation influences their recruitment process. One of the teachers noted that:

“Individual schools or school networks may have specific policies or preferences related to cultural orientation in their recruitment processes”.

Policy frameworks often emphasize qualifications, experience, and competency standards, but there is a growing recognition of the importance of cultural competence in education. Current policies in Zambia typically prioritize academic qualifications and teaching experience over cultural orientation (MoE, 2019). However, there is an emerging discourse on the need for teachers to understand and respect diverse cultural backgrounds within the classroom. This shift is partly influenced by global trends towards inclusive education and the recognition of cultural diversity as an asset in educational settings (OECD, 2013). Regulations governing teacher recruitment in Lusaka District reflect broader national objectives of promoting quality education and equitable opportunities for all students. While cultural orientation may not be explicitly stated in recruitment criteria, there are efforts to integrate cultural sensitivity into professional development programs and teaching standards (NPA, 2011). Challenges persist, including the subjective nature of assessing cultural competence during recruitment, potential biases in selection processes, and the need for clearer guidelines on integrating cultural orientation into educational practices. Addressing these challenges requires ongoing dialogue between educational policymakers, school administrators, and teachers themselves to ensure that recruitment practices align with inclusive educational goals while maintaining standards of academic excellence.

5. CONCLUSION

The teacher recruitment and selection process in selected international secondary schools within Lusaka District, Zambia, reveals critical insights into the practices and challenges faced in securing high-quality educators. Across these institutions, a rigorous selection framework is evident, emphasizing not only academic qualifications but also teaching experience, pedagogical approaches, and alignment with the school's mission and values. This holistic approach aims to ensure that teachers not only possess subject expertise but also demonstrate a commitment to student-centered learning and holistic development. Moreover, the recruitment process underscores the importance of cultural competence and adaptability among teachers. International schools in Lusaka District prioritize candidates who can navigate diverse cultural backgrounds and contribute to a globally minded educational environment. This emphasis reflects the schools' commitment to fostering intercultural understanding and preparing students for an interconnected world. Despite these strengths, challenges persist, particularly regarding the equitable representation of local educators within the international school sector. The recruitment process often favors candidates with international experience or qualifications, potentially limiting opportunities for talented local teachers. Addressing this imbalance requires concerted efforts to provide pathways for professional development and career advancement for Zambian educators

within international school settings. Looking forward, enhancing transparency and inclusivity in the recruitment process can further strengthen these institutions' ability to attract and retain top-tier teaching talent. By continuously refining recruitment strategies to encompass broader diversity and inclusivity goals, international secondary schools in Lusaka District can better fulfill their mission of delivering high-quality education that meets both global standards and local needs. While the teacher recruitment and selection process in Lusaka's international secondary schools demonstrates commendable efforts to uphold rigorous standards and foster a globally oriented learning environment, ongoing efforts are needed to promote greater diversity, equity, and inclusion. By nurturing a cadre of skilled educators who embody both local relevance and global perspectives, these institutions can better prepare students to thrive in a complex and interconnected world.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study. These recommendations aim to improve the effectiveness of teacher recruitment and selection processes, contributing to the overall quality of education and school community dynamics in international secondary schools in Lusaka District, Zambia.

Standardization of Selection Criteria:

- The government should implement standardized criteria for evaluating candidates that align with the school's values, educational philosophy, and specific needs. This could include academic qualifications, teaching experience, pedagogical skills, and alignment with the school's mission.

Enhanced Diversity and Inclusivity:

- The government should actively promote diversity and inclusivity in the recruitment process by ensuring a diverse pool of candidates is considered. This could involve outreach efforts to attract candidates from different backgrounds, regions, and cultural perspectives, thereby enriching the school community.

Streamlined and Transparent Process:

- The ministry of education should establish clear and transparent procedures for the recruitment and selection process. This includes defining roles and responsibilities of selection committee members, communicating timelines to candidates, providing feedback where possible, and ensuring that decisions are based on fair and objective evaluation criteria.

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Received: 2 July 2024
Revised: 16 July 2024
Accepted: 20 July 2024
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Received: 2 July 2024

Revised: 16 July 2024

Accepted: 20 July 2024

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.12786611](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12786611)

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Citations: Lufupa, L., Mubemba, B. N., & Chanda, C. T. (2024). **Teacher Recruitment and Selection Process: A Case of Selected International Secondary Schools in Lusaka District, Zambia.**